
A Review on the next generation Colon-Targeted Drug Delivery System

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Abstract

Colonic drug delivery may increase drug absorption, reduce side effects, and make it easier to reach particular therapeutic targets. Because of the distinct physiological environment of the colon, distribution of medications to the colon requires careful formulation creation, as both oral and rectal dose forms may present challenges. The creation of new medications is essential to their effectiveness because colonic drug delivery is being used in an increasing range of therapeutic applications. This review provides a modern viewpoint on the crucial elements impacting the successful development and introduction of drugs that target the colon. A review of key physiological factors affecting the release, solubility, stability, and absorption of medications in the colon is followed by an outline of the best colon-targeted formulation techniques. Finally, the most appropriate preclinical research carried out in vitro, in vivo, and in silico is presented in order to encourage the intentional development of new colon cancer treatments.

Keywords: Colon-targeted Drug delivery system; Gastrointestinal disorders; Machine learning; Artificial Intelligence

1. Introduction

The discovery of numerous pharmaceutical benefits and potential in recent years has led to a resurgence of colonic medication administration. Improved local disease therapy, access to local therapeutic targets, less systemic drug exposure and related toxicity, and even increased drug bioavailability can all be facilitated by targeting medications to the colon. Colonic medication delivery has historically been centered on treating local conditions, including colorectal cancer and inflammatory bowel disease (IBD). Colonic medication delivery maximizes drug concentration at the target site while minimizing systemic exposure, which can enhance the treatment of local illnesses. As the colonic and rectal environments are better characterized, novel local targets such as the lymphatic system, enteric immune system, and microbiome are becoming recognized. These new targets may make it easier to treat systemic diseases and disorders affecting distant organs, in addition to colonic illnesses. For instance, it has been found that the intestinal microbiota influences neurological disorders like Parkinson's and Alzheimer's disease, dyslipidemia, urinary tract infections, and traumatic spinal cord injuries. Additionally, targeting the mesenteric lymphatic system may help cure insulin resistance and improve brain accessibility. Probiotics, postbiotics, vaccines, oligonucleotides, and biologics are only a few of the novel therapy modalities that have generated increased interest in colonic administration due to their development as possible therapeutic targets and advancements in pharmaceutical sciences.

Oral dosage forms with colon-specific release and rectal administration are two formulations that facilitate colonic medication delivery. The first formulation, a pH-sensitive methacrylate polymer sold under the brand name

Eudragit® S (Evonik), allows for targeted drug delivery to the terminal ileum/proximal colon (also known as ileocolonic delivery) by oral means and was published in 1982. When the pH of the intestines rises above 7.0, Eudragit® S, a synthetic copolymer made of poly(methacrylic acid, methyl methacrylate) at a 1:2 ratio, dissolves. Eudragit® S is therefore utilized as an enteric coating for oral dosage forms intended for terminal ileal medication release. As of right now, it is a widely used technology found in a number of commercial formulations, most notably Asacol® (Tillotts Pharma) and Lialda®/Mezavant® (Cosmo Pharmaceuticals), which are designed to deliver mesalazine to the colon for the treatment of IBD. Nonetheless, there has long been doubt about the efficacy of pH-sensitive polymers for colonic medication administration. According to human research, enteric coatings exhibit variable release patterns; in certain people, the coatings dissolve early or stay intact. A portion of patients experiences this discrepancy, which results from variations in intestinal pH, and does not receive the recommended dosage of their medication. Additionally, the pathophysiology of the illness may increase the risk of enteric coating failure; for instance, gut pH is often significantly lower in IBD patients than in healthy individuals.

When it comes to rectal medicine delivery, there are a few pros and cons that differ from oral or colonic delivery. Rectal formulations, for example, do not have to pass through the upper GI tract to reach the colon; hence, they are less susceptible to intra- and inter-patient physiological variability. The rectal environment is more stable when the colon is empty, which makes it easier for drugs to release and absorb over time. Additionally, medicines that have unfavorable taste profiles, irritate the gastrointestinal tract, are unstable in the upper GI tract, or significantly undergo hepatic first-pass metabolism may benefit from rectal administration. When safe swallowing is compromised—due to dysphagia, unconsciousness, or in individuals at extreme age—the rectal route may also be helpful. Rectal formulations are often less popular than oral formulations, despite these benefits. Some of the reasons for this include cultural misconceptions, simplicity of administration, and invasiveness. Mechanistically, rectal formulations typically cannot carry medications past the colon's splenic flexure and may also encounter retention issues. Because of this, they are usually most effective in treating diseases that are localized to the rectum and distal colon, though systemic products, like vaccinations, are starting to be investigated. Rectal formulations come in a variety of forms, the most popular ones being gels, foams, enemas, and suppositories. The distribution of small molecule medications in simple solutions, emulsions, or suspensions for the treatment of pain, nausea, and vomiting, hemorrhoids, constipation, and IBD has been the main emphasis of rectal administration in the past. But increasingly sophisticated and diverse formulations have been studied recently, both in preclinical and clinical settings. These formulations can provide ideas for optimizing the delivery route's potential.

2. Anatomy and physiology of the colon:

The large intestine extends from the distal end of the ileum to the anus. The human large intestine is about 1.5 meters long. The colon is the upper five feet of the large intestine and is mainly situated in the abdomen. The colon is a cylindrical tube that is lined by moist, soft pink lining called mucosa; the pathway is called the lumen and is approximately 2-3 inches in diameter. The cecum forms the first part of the colon and leads to the right colon or the ascending colon (just under the liver), followed by the transverse colon, the descending colon, sigmoid colon, rectum, and the anal canal (Figure 1). The physiology of the proximal and distal colon differs in several respects that can have an effect on drug absorption at each site. The physical properties of the luminal content of the colon also change, from liquid in the cecum to semisolid in the distal colon. The major functions of the colon are the consolidation of the intestinal contents into feces by the absorption of water and electrolytes and to store the feces until excretion.

Colon

Figure 1: Anatomy of the colon

The colon has an extremely high absorptive capacity; about 90% of the 2000 ml of fluid that enters the colon each day through the ileocecal valve is absorbed. In addition, the colon's contents must be expelled at the appropriate time, and water and Na^+ must be absorbed from the lumen in order to concentrate the fecal content, secrete K^+ and (HCO_3^-) , and create an environment that is favorable for the growth of colonic microorganisms like *Bacteroides*, *Eubacterium*, and *Enterobacteriaceae*.

3. pH in the colon:

There can be differences in pH across and within subjects in the gastrointestinal system. The pH of the gastrointestinal fluid is influenced by food consumption, illness status, and diet. One method of targeted colon medication administration has been the change in pH along the gastrointestinal tract. In the gastrointestinal tract, there is a pH gradient that peaks at roughly 7.5 in the distal small intestine and varies from 1.2 in the stomach to 6.6 in the proximal small intestine. Historically, drugs have been delivered to the small intestine via pH-sensitive enteric coatings, which take advantage of the pH difference between the stomach and the small intestine.

4. Targeting Approaches for Colon Drug Delivery

4.1. Multiparticulate drug delivery systems.

In order to prevent dose dumping in a specific area of the colon, modified-release formulations containing multiparticulates such as pellets, granules, or microspheres compressed into tablets or encapsulated in capsules have been devised to provide prolonged release throughout the colon. They ensure homogeneous dispersion over the affected areas of the colon to maximize therapeutic efficacy upon breakdown of the capsule shell or tablet. They also ensure consistent absorption and are less susceptible to the effects of food. An enteric polymer coating on the tablets or capsules shields the stomach and small intestine system. Afterwards, the compressed or encapsulated particles are discharged into the cecum or distal ileum and disperse evenly throughout the area. Every particle or pellet functions as a separate drug delivery system, releasing the medication in a regulated way. Siepmann et al. made beads laden with 5-aminosalicylic acid and coated them in various Nutriose: ethylcellulose mixtures. Studies on in vitro release were conducted using culture media containing colonic bacteria and fresh feces slurries from patients with inflammatory bowel disorders. In media containing feces slurries, it was discovered that the medication release from the coated pellets increased dramatically and then persisted in a sustained way. The starch derivative utilized in this study, called Nutriose, is said to be selectively broken down by enzymes generated by colonic bacteria seen in patients with ulcerative colitis and Crohn's disease.

ABC

4.2. Time-dependent systems

In order to achieve low drug release in the upper gastrointestinal tract - the stomach and small intestine - and maximal drug release in the colonic region - the colonic residence time - these kinds of systems use rate-controlling high viscosity polymers. The drug delivery systems take an average of five to six hours to transit through the small intestine and stomach (three hours in each location). However, the length of time it takes for a drug delivery system to take effect varies depending on the kind and quantity of food consumed. Drug delivery device gastrointestinal transit can be significantly affected by peristalsis, the movement of the gastrointestinal tract. Additionally, medical disorders such as diarrhea with predominant irritable bowel syndrome can increase the velocity of transit and cause the drug delivery device to defecate before there has been adequate drug release. Due to these factors, time-dependent systems are not always reliable. As a result, pH and time-dependent system combinations are frequently created, which offer a better strategy for targeted medication in the colon.

In these hybrid systems, the drug delivery apparatus is coated with a pH-dependent polymer that dissolves in the small intestine. Subsequently, the inner core, composed of polymers that sustain release, releases a reduced quantity of the drug in the small intestine and the highest possible amount in the colon. Such a pH- and time-dependent mechanism for colon-specific mesalamine administration was created by Patel *et al.* Hydroxypropyl methylcellulose, a hydrophilic polymer that is pH-independent hydrophilic polymer, was used to cover the mesalamine core tablet. Then, Eudragit S100, a pH-dependent methacrylic acid polymer, was applied for one more coat to the core tablet. It was discovered through *in-vitro* testing that the device may demonstrate site-specific colon medication delivery that is site-specific.

4.3. Pressure-controlled systems:

Because the luminal pressure from peristalsis is higher in the colon due to the high viscosity of the colonic contents and the significantly lower fluid content compared to the upper parts of the gastrointestinal tract, such as the stomach or small intestine, very few new devices for colon targeting have been developed. The membrane containing the medication opens up under the increased luminal pressure in the colon, and the pressure-controlled devices are designed to withstand the luminal pressure in the upper gastrointestinal tract. The collapse time can be adjusted by varying the membrane's thickness. Pressure-controlled colon delivery capsules (PCDCs) were created by Shibata *et al.* to increase the bioavailability of glycyrrhizin in a solution. Eight different kinds of glycyrrhizin solutions were created and then placed within PCDCs. The capsules were tested in beagle dogs *in vivo*. It was found that the self-emulsifying drug delivery system significantly increased the bioavailability of glycyrrhizin in the colon.

4.4. Osmotically controlled systems

These systems have a clear advantage over others since they use osmotic pressure to control medication release from the drug delivery devices rather than relying on the physiological circumstances of the gastrointestinal tract. The solubility and osmotic pressure of the core components, the size of the delivery aperture, and the type of rate-controlling membrane are examples of formulation parameters that may affect drug release. In their most basic configuration, these devices have a drug-containing inner core - with or without an osmogen - encircled by a semi-permeable membrane with a regulated drug release aperture. Water seeps into the center of this system through the semi-permeable membrane when it comes into contact with gastrointestinal secretions. Depending on the size of the hole and the solubility of the drug, the drug within the core generates a saturated solution that is subsequently delivered via the orifice in a regulated manner. Such systems are applicable to moderately soluble medicines. Push-pull mechanisms can be utilized for medicines with exceptional solubility. These systems have two layers with a semi-permeable membrane covering them. Polymeric osmotic agents make up the inner compartment, whereas drug core and osmogents make up the outer compartment. The medicine is forced through the membrane's opening by the swelling polymers in the inner compartment when water is absorbed through the membrane and enters the system. Alza Corp.'s OROS-CT was created to transport medications specifically to the colon, while it can also be used to administer drugs systemically. It is composed of one or more than five or six enteric-coated push-pull delivery devices housed in a hard gelatin capsule.

5. Innovative methods for Colon targeted drug delivery

5.1. Rectal drug delivery

Rectal preparations, such as enemas, foams, gels, and suppositories, are frequently used to treat constipation, hemorrhoids, pain, nausea, and vomiting, as well as IBD using 5-ASA and corticosteroids. Rectal preparations have evolved in recent years from conventional formulations to more sophisticated ones that, depending on the particular application, can support systemic absorption as well as local drug retention. Three different kinds of enemas have been identified in this regard.

(a) Severely hypotonic enemas cause the body to absorb drugs and circulate them.

(b) hypertonic enemas that accelerate systemic medication absorption by causing bodily fluids to be secreted into the lumen.

(c) High local drug bioavailability is achieved through moderately hypotonic enemas with feces-like ionic compositions, while minimizing systemic medication absorption is minimized.

In this case, the drug's bioavailability is significantly influenced by the osmolality of rectal preparations. Epithelial tissue in the colon actively pumps sodium ions into the lumen to facilitate the absorption of water. Therefore, it is possible to use this intrinsic characteristic to osmotically guide medicines into the epithelium. This can be accomplished by making rectal formulations less tonic, which creates an osmotic gradient that allows hydrophilic medications and mucus-penetrating nanoparticles to pass through the surface of the epithelial tissue without causing harm. For instance, a study comparing three different types of enemas loaded with tenofovir revealed that, in contrast to isotonic and hypertonic preparations, which led to rapid systemic drug absorption, hypotonic sodium-based enemas boosted drug concentration in mice colonic tissues.

5.2. pH-, microbiota-, and time-triggered combination systems:

An enhanced colon-targeted medication delivery system that includes three separate trigger mechanisms was proposed by Moutaharrik et al. in a recent study. The two layers of the coating in this system are made up of an inner, time-dependent, swellable cellulose derivative (HPMC, hydroxypropyl cellulose; HPC) that is encircled by a combination of a pH-dependent polymer (Eudragit® S) and a microbiota-triggered polysaccharide (high-amylose starch, Amylo N460). In vitro and ex vivo models of the cellulose derivatives Eudragit® S and Amylo N460 demonstrated consistent colon-targeting efficacy, indicating the success of this first instance of a triple colon-targeting mechanism. In light of these encouraging preliminary findings, the system's continued development in in vivo models seems promising.

5.3. pH- and time-triggered combination systems.

Although they are less common, various pH- and time-dependent parallel systems have been studied. One such instance is the coating of 5-ASA pellets with or without inulin by combining two enteric polymers (Eudragit® S and L) with a time-dependent polymer (Eudragit® RS). After testing the mixture at various ratios and coating thicknesses, it was discovered that a 16:64:20 w/w ratio of Eudragit® S:L:RS at a 15% coating thickness worked best for colon-targeted drug delivery in in vitro studies. The coated pellets exhibited notably superior therapeutic effects than the Pentasa product (pH-only triggered) in a rat model of ulcerative colitis. It should be highlighted that there was no discernible therapeutic difference between the inulin-containing and non-inulin-containing pellets, indicating that the additional therapeutic advantage was provided by the combination as well as the time- and pH-triggered mechanisms.

An alternative method was compress-coating flurbiprofen tablets with both Eudragit® S100 and sodium alginate (SA) alone. In contrast to using SA alone, the pH-dependent polymer in the coating inhibited drug release and prevented SA from swelling in the stomach area when tested in healthy humans. This led to a higher concentration of the drug in the colon. These results were supported by in vivo X-ray imaging, which demonstrated that the tablets' structural integrity was maintained during their passage to the colon. [Phloral®](#)

The first dual-triggered colonic drug delivery technology to be successfully sold was the Phloral® system. It is a one-layer coating system made of a uniform blend of resistant starch (amylopectin and amylose) and Eudragit® S.

Owing to their separate trigger mechanisms, the two parts function in tandem and can compensate for each other's inactivity if one stops working. The Eudragit® S mechanism in this system ensures that the tablet's integrity is preserved during its passage through the small intestine and stomach. It also controls the swelling of the starch by acting as a structural agent. In contrast, resistant starch acts as a substrate for the microbiota in the colon, offering a backup plan for initiating medication release in the event that Eudragit® S's essential pH threshold is not reached. Regardless of the patient's feeding status, Phloral® technology has, in fact, demonstrated successful effects in the treatment of IBD. Phloral® has also been effectively used to treat obesity and infections caused by *Clostridium difficile*.

5.4. Multi-stimulus systems for colonic drug delivery via the oral route

Formulation techniques that rely on a single physiological stimulus (pH, transit duration, or microbial enzymes) for colonic medication administration have been shown to be significantly variable in terms of targeting efficacy between and within patients. Therefore, it has been demonstrated in recent years that combining drug release mechanisms based on multiple physiological stimuli is a more reliable method. These combination or multifaceted systems can be categorized as sequential or parallel trigger systems based on their design. The drug release mechanism of a sequential trigger system unfolds layer by layer, starting from the outermost layer and working its way into the core, using several matrices divided into distinct layers. In this way, drug release depends on the physiological stimulus that activates each layer in turn. A parallel system, in juxtaposition, involves several drug release mechanisms operating concurrently. Independent triggering mechanisms in parallel systems are usually activated simultaneously by combining them into a single layer.

In this view, medication release should still occur through other pathways even if one route fails due to physiological variability (i.e.g., fails to achieve a pH-mediated dissolving threshold or cannot be metabolized by intestinal bacteria). As such, parallel systems are the most dependable approach to developing novel colon-targeted medications. In terms of colonic drug delivery, multi-stimuli coatings for tablets, capsules, and pellets have achieved the most translational success to date. Oral nanomedicines targeting the colon with multiple stimuli have the potential to be developed. Despite their rarity, these systems have not yet produced noteworthy outcomes in human research. The safety of materials for oral delivery must be taken into consideration when creating new targeted formulations. The United States Food and Drug Administration (FDA) has classified a number of materials used in colonic delivery as Generally Recognized As Safe (GRAS). These materials include polysaccharides for microbiota-triggered release, Eudragit® polymers for pH-triggered release, and hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC) for time-triggered release. The choice of a colon-targeting system for novel medications will be contingent upon several indication-specific factors, including the medication to be administered, the ailment to be addressed, and any pathophysiological consequences that could modify the gastrointestinal milieu.

6. Conclusions

Colonic drug delivery is in a fascinating stage of development where new insights into the distinct physiology of the colon, efficient formulation techniques, and sophisticated *in vitro*, *in vivo*, and *in silico* technologies can be used to create innovative and successful medications. This review has explained how the conditions in the GI tract should guide the development of colon-targeted medicine at every step: from identifying targets specific to the colon to designing formulations that deliver drugs to the intended site of action with consistency, to evaluating formulations preclinically. The development of parallel-trigger formulation technologies has improved the oral colonic drug delivery's dependability and created new avenues for the targeted modulation of developing systemic targets or the more effective management of regional illnesses.

Subsequent investigations may build upon these formulation techniques to create indication-specific formulations, in which the drug release triggers are tailored to certain patient populations or may be based on pathophysiology. Furthermore, there is a great deal of room for innovation in rectal drug delivery, where cutting-edge methods (such as *in silico* design or precision formulation) might be applied to address the difficulties the administration route is now encountering. Expanding physiologically appropriate methods for PK evaluation of rectal formulations and

standardizing in vitro and in vivo models for PK evaluation of oral colon-targeted medications represent additional opportunities.

Lastly, additional research illustrating the ways in which sophisticated in silico tools can be utilised to minimise the costs and duration involved in creating colon-targeted medications would be helpful in encouraging other researchers to embrace similar technologies. Recent developments in the design and development of colon-targeted medications offer significant opportunities for bringing safer and more effective treatments to the clinic.

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